

MISTAKES IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AND THEIR INTERACTIVE SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Today, in the era of rapid development and globalization, the demand for young personnel who master the days is increasing as production increases. This is the basis for popular young people to increase their interest in languages and learn foreign languages. But a number of mistakes are made in the process of learning languages produced by students. In this article, we will analyze some of the mistakes, problematic products and documents that young people who are new to developing languages make.

Key words: *method, interactivity, student, foreign languages, educational programs, educational load.*

ОШИБКИ В ИЗУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА И ИХ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В условиях современной стремительно развивающейся глобализации спрос на молодые кадры, владеющие иностранными языками, возрастает с каждым днем. Это является причиной повышения интереса к иностранным языкам среди молодежи и широкой популярности изучения иностранных языков. Однако из-за того, что студенты в процессе изучения иностранных языков допускают ряд ошибок или сталкиваются с некоторыми проблемными ситуациями, возникает и ситуация, когда их энтузиазм к новым языкам, которые они изучают, быстро пропадает. В этой статье мы рассмотрим некоторые ошибки, проблемные ситуации и их анализ, которые совершают молодые люди, только приступившие к изучению иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: *метод, интерактивность, студент, иностранные языки, образовательные программы, учебная нагрузка.*

INTRODUCTION

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As one of the means of knowing and communicating with the surrounding world, a foreign language occupies a special place in the modern education system due to its social, cognitive and developmental functions. Taking into account that the position of the Russian language as a leading means of international communication in the world is becoming stronger and there are no serious trends to stop or slow down this process, the problem of using effective methods in this regard is being posed.

DISCUSSION

Learning Russian is very important. Of course, every person aims to achieve a certain goal by doing something. Along with this, new language learners who start learning English, Russian, French, German or any other Eastern languages aim to achieve a certain goal and result by learning these languages. Unfortunately, some language learners make mistakes at this step and face a number of difficulties later in the language learning process. Another problem faced by young learners who are just beginning to learn foreign languages is their fear of making mistakes while learning and using the language. Of course, avoiding making mistakes in the process of language learning builds the ability of language learners to be responsible for the language, but this process slows down language learning and the learner gradually loses the ability to speak the language. may lead to difficulties in full development. Usually, a language learner tries to avoid making mistakes in grammatical norms during conversation in the language he is learning, which causes him to confuse the content of the thought being spoken. This causes the listener to not fully understand the idea. It should not be forgotten that mistakes and shortcomings are natural in any newly started work. Pronunciation disorders and grammatical errors in the speech of new language learners can be solved by constant self-improvement and practice of speaking the language. Another mistake made by new language learners is to rely too much on the teacher's support and avoid working on themselves. Of course, it is optimal to rely on the teacher's explanations and help in the process of language learning, but it is a solution to minor complications related to language learning that occur in the process of independent work, when students avoid working on themselves or work less on themselves. Failure to find them will lead to slow learners' language learning skills and poor results. It should not be forgotten that foreign language skills cannot be built based on the speech of one person, because usually the speech of teachers in that foreign language is very different from the speech of native speakers of that foreign language. One of the best ways to avoid such problems is to watch movies and listen to podcasts and radio broadcasts in that language. One of the problems faced by new

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foreign language learners is the overabundance of foreign language programs and the inability of young people to choose the most suitable training programs and then transfer them to training programs. is the inability to get away. What method is sometimes more effective in learning foreign languages? face-to-face learning with a teacher or in groups? This question arises in front of young people who have just started learning the language. Observations show that the above two methods of learning foreign languages have their own advantages and disadvantages. For example, by studying foreign languages in groups, it is possible to quickly develop the ability to speak a foreign language, and to strengthen the information learned in the lesson through mutual questions and answers.

In the modern sense, the educational process is considered as a process of interaction between the teacher and students to introduce students to certain knowledge, skills, abilities and values. Each teaching method organically includes the educational work of the teacher (presentation, explanation of new material) and the organization of active learning and cognitive activities of students. That is, the teacher, on the one hand, explains the educational material himself, on the other hand, he tries to stimulate the learning and cognitive activity of students (encourages them to think, draw independent conclusions, etc.)

A foreign language lesson is considered as a social phenomenon, where the class is a certain social environment where the teacher and students enter into certain social relations with each other, the learning process is an interaction of all participants. At the same time, success in learning is the result of collective use of all opportunities for learning. And students have to contribute a lot to this process. In all classifications there are methods of verbal presentation of knowledge. These include story, explanation, explanation, conversation, briefing. Verbal methods are used at all stages of learning: during preparation for mastering new material, during its explanation, assimilation, generalization and application.

The "Round Discussion" method is of great importance in mastering the Russian language. It is known that in the method, the teacher formulates a problem and offers students a task. The student can evaluate the importance of the problem in the process. Students will be able to talk about the issue presented. They discuss their positions and come to a common decision. One well-known method is Brainstorming, which focuses on problem solving rather than discussing it. However, according to this method of teaching English, the audience is divided into two groups - "idea generators" who actually propose ideas, and "experts" who evaluate the position of each at the end of the "attack".

When using the selected methods in Russian, the following criteria should be followed:

1. Your level of preparation;
2. How much time you can devote to lessons;
3. Financial opportunities;
4. Their priorities and desires.

Also, information can be absorbed more easily in the following ways: by ear, through a textbook, with the help of video lessons, in a playful way, etc. The student's interests are also taken into account. His opinion and personal interests should not be ignored. In order to help the student as much as possible, it is necessary to explain the channel of his perception and, accordingly, the direction of tasks.

A conversation is a dialogue: teacher's questions and students' answers. The student's mind follows the teacher's mind, as a result of which the students move step by step in acquiring new knowledge. According to the appointment, interviews are divided into: 1) introductory or organizational; 2) communication of new knowledge; 3) synthesize or identify; 4) control and correction. According to the level of cognitive independence of students, reproductive and heuristic conversations are distinguished.

An introductory (preparatory) interview is usually held before the start of the training. Its purpose is to determine whether students correctly understand the meaning of the upcoming work, have a good idea of what and how to do it. Interview (explanation) can be: question-and-answer, avoiding objections, memorizing answers; Socratic (gentle, respected by the student, but allowing doubts and objections); heuristic (putting the student in front of problems and demanding his own answers to the questions posed by the teacher). All types of conversation are used in elementary school.

Synthesizing (final or reinforcing) conversations serve to summarize and systematize the knowledge available to schoolchildren, and control-corrective (checking) conversations are used for diagnostic purposes, as well as for the development, clarification, and completion of new facts or rules. is used when knowledge that students have. In order to conduct the interview successfully, the teacher must seriously prepare for it. It is necessary to clearly define the topic of the interview, its purpose, create a plan-concept, choose visual aids, form the main and auxiliary questions that may arise during the interview, and think about the methodology of its organization and conduct.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that in order to avoid problems and problems in the process of learning the desired languages, it is necessary to be more responsible for language learning, to work on yourself regularly. Success in any task, not just language learning, requires consistency. Only then can you fully master the language being studied.

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